

EFFECT OF SILANE COUPLING TREATMENT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES IN PLASTIC REINFORCED WITH PLAIN WOVEN FABRIC

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ABSTRACT

In woven fabric composite under tensile loading, microfracture occurred in the transverse fiber bundle at the initial stage of the tensile test. Knee-point on the stress-strain curve was appeared due to the occurrence of the microfracture. The microfracture is defined as the first fracture phenomenon during tensile test. The stress at the microfracture is known to be affected by interfacial strength and can be used as the index of fiber/matrix interface.

In this study, combination material constants of interface element was determined checking the value of initial microfracture stress obtained by numerical analysis against initial microfracture stress of plain woven fabric composites.

INTRODUCTION

Low interface properties lead to inferior composite properties, although reinforced fiber and matrix posses high mechanical properties. Therefore interface in composite materials has significant important role. Scientific research activities for interface are roughly divided into two categories. One is chemical aspects and another category is mechanical aspects. The former groups have mainly discussed chemical reaction and chemical structure on interface and/or in interphase. The latter groups have been making efforts to develop mechanical estimation techniques. There are many estimation methods for mechanical properties of interface[1-2]. Among these methods we investigated relation between mechanical properties of plain woven glass fabric composites and fiber/matrix interface by single-layer plain woven fabric composites. Knee-point in tensile stress-strain relation was appeared due to initiation of the microfracture under tensile load. The initial microfracture occurred at the fiber/matrix interface or resin close to the interface in transverse fiber bundle. The initial microfracture was defined as the first fracture under tensile test, and limitation of elastic regions. The initial microfracture stress was affected by interfacial strength and could be evaluated as the index of fiber/matrix interface [3].

In order to understand microfracture mechanism of composites finite element analysis is very useful technique so that local stress states affect greatly microfracture. Our proposed finite element model represented the three-dimensional fiber orientation states using three-dimensional beam elements[4]. In the modeling, it is necessary to consider not only the properties of matrix and reinforcement but also those of fiber/matrix interphase. Unfortunately, we have not known material constants of interphase; E_i , σ_i and so on (suffix "i" indicates interface). This fact prevents us from developing composite materials.

In this study, the initial microfracture stress was used to determine the material constants of interface. Both numerical and experimental analyses were carried out to obtain initial microfracture stress. Elastic modulus of interface; E_i and strength of interface; σ_i were determined to coincide with numerical and experimental results. From proposed method in this paper combination of elastic modulus and strength of interface could be obtained. This was the first attempt in interface research of composite materials.

Figure 1 shows schematic diagram of FEM models and finite element divisions in two loading conditions. One is that the load is applied along the fiber(0/90) and another is $\pm 45^\circ$ direction (± 45). The models were consisted of three-dimensional beam elements to approximate geometry of the plain woven fabric. In considering the microfracture in the fiber bundle, a fiber bundle was divided into a pair of paralleled beam elements, and between divided fiber elements the beam that has mechanical properties of interphase was arranged. At the intersection of the fiber bundles, the beam element was mounted to transmit the force between fiber bundles. At the surface of the composite, the elements with resin properties were also mounted. These resin elements were orientated both the loading direction and transverse direction.

Figure 1 Schematic diagrams and FEM divisions.

The material constants used are shown as Table 1. The fiber bundle properties were calculated by Law of Mixture as unidirectional glass/epoxy composites with 60% of fiber volume fraction. Here both elastic modulus and strength of interface element and intersection element are unknown values.

Table 1 Material constants.

	Elastic modulus(GPa)	Strength(MPa)
Fiber bundle element	47.5	870
Resin element	3.2	80
Intersection element	3.2~47.5	
Interface element	3.2~47.5	

The outline of analysis procedure is shown in Figure 2 as a flowchart. At first the elastic modulus of intersection element (E_c) and the strength of intersection element (σ_c) are assumed. The initial microfracture stresses in each 0/90 and ± 45 are obtained by numerical analysis with various elastic moduli of interface element (E_i) under assumed strength. As a result, the coefficient of a_i and a_c was evaluated as the ratio of experimental value to calculated value. Strength of elements (σ_i^* , σ_c^*) are determined multiplying assumed strength (σ_i , σ_c) by coefficient (a_i , a_c) under assumed interfacial modulus (E_i). Thus the strength of interface element and intersection element was obtained. According to the definition of initial microfracture, the most important point in this method is the microfracture occurred in the transverse fiber bundle in 0/90 and at the fiber intersection in ± 45 . Moreover materials constants (E_i , σ_i^* , E_c , σ_c^*) should be assumed as same values in both 0/90 and ± 45 . Therefore materials constants should be satisfied with following two relationships.

$$T_{(0/90)} < T_{c(0/90)} \times a_c \tag{1}$$

$$T_{(\pm 45)} < T_{i(\pm 45)} \times a_i \tag{2}$$

Here, $T_{(0/90)}$ and $T_{(\pm 45)}$ are as experimental values in each 0/90 and ± 45 respectively. Each T_i and T_c defines as a calculated tensile stress of model where interface and intersection element fail. The values of elastic modulus of interface element and intersection element ranged from 3.2GPa to 47.5GPa. E_i and E_c values below 3.2GPa are unreal value because it was lower than the value of resin element, and E_i and E_c values above 47.5GPa are also unreal value because it is higher than the value of fiber bundle elements. The combination of materials constants (E_i , σ_i^* , E_c , σ_c^*) are determined through these process.

Figure 2 Flowchart.

Figure 3 shows boundary condition in this numerical analysis. Flat face is kept on the AC and BD due to modeling a part of specimen. Moreover displacement in the width direction on the AC and BD has to be considered due to Poisson's ratio. Therefore the displacement in the width direction the AC and BD are constant. The constants displacements were applied the nodes on AB. Von Mises failure criterion was used to fracture process analysis. Force in the load direction in each element is calculated from axial and shear force occurring in fiber bundle elements, resin elements and interface elements. Total of these forces is tensile load and tensile stress is obtained dividing the tensile load by sectional area. Also, strain is equal to load displacement divided by length of model.

Figure 3 Boundary condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 lists the initial microfracture stress obtained by experimental results. In the experiment, the initial microfracture stress of material treated by silane coupling agent was 67MPa in 0/90($T_{(0/90)}$), whereas in ± 45 the initial microfracture stress was 34MPa($T_{(\pm 45)}$).

Table 2 Experimental value.

Initial microfracture stress(0/90)	67MPa
(± 45)	34MPa

Figure 4 shows the example of relation between initial microfracture stress obtained by calculation and interfacial modulus.

Figure 4 Relation between calculated tensile stress and Interfacial modulus.

Strength of interface element assumed 80MPa(α) and elastic modulus of intersection element assumed 3.2GPa(E_i) in this calculation. For example, in case that value of interfacial modulus is 3.2GPa, at point (A) failure of interface element occurs under applied tensile stress of 259MPa($T_{i(0/90)}$) in this model. In order to coincide with the initial microfracture stress of the experimental value (67MPa), the interfacial strength should be 21MPa(α^*) which means assumed interfacial strength (80MPa) multiplied by 0.26(a_i). As same way, relation between interfacial strength and interfacial modulus is obtained as shown Figure 5.

Figure 5 Relation between interfacial strength and interfacial modulus($E_c=3.2GPa$).

The microfracture occurs intersection at fibers in ± 45 . When the value of interfacial modulus is 3.2GPa, failure of the intersection element occurs under applied tensile stress of 163MPa($T_{\alpha\pm 45}$) at point (B) in Figure 4. In order to coincide with the initial microfracture stress of the experimental value (34MPa), a_c become 0.21(34/163) strength of intersection element should be 17MPa. Here, again, 17MPa(α^*) means assumed strength of intersection element (80MPa) multiplied by 0.21. In ± 45 relation between strength of intersection element and interfacial modulus as shown in Figure 6 is obtained.

Figure 6 Relation between the strength of intersection element and interfacial modulus($E_c=3.2GPa$).

The combination of material constants can be determined by Figures 5 and 6 when E_c is 3.2GPa. However α^* and α^* in 0/90 should be equal with those in ± 45 . Therefore the following procedure should be carried out. The value($T_{i(\pm 45)} \times a_i$) of interface element in ± 45 multiplied by coefficient a_i should be bigger than experimental value in ± 45 (34MPa). The value($T_{\alpha(0/90)} \times a_c$) of intersection element multiplied by coefficient a_c should be bigger than experimental value in 0/90(67MPa). For example, as shown Figure 7, when E_i is 3.2GPa, α^* should be also 17MPa

in 0/90. $84\text{MPa}(T_{c(0/90)}\alpha_c)$ means calculated value(401MPa , $T_{c(0/90)}$) in interface element multiplied α_c . This value (84MPa) is higher than experimental value(67MPa , $T_{(0/90)}$) because the initial microfracture in ± 45 occurs the intersection at fibers. As same way, it should be considered the initial microfracture in 0/90 occurs the fiber/matrix interface. When E_i is 3.2GPa , α^* should be also 21MPa in ± 45 . $42\text{MPa}(T_{i(\pm 45)}\alpha_i)$ means calculated value(163MPa , $T_{i(\pm 45)}$) in intersection element multiplied α_c . This value (42MPa) is higher than experimental value(34MPa , $T_{(\pm 45)}$) because the initial microfracture in ± 45 occurs in intersection at fibers.

Figure 7 Determination process of material constants combinations.

Figure 8 and 9 show the combination of materials constants of interface element and intersection element. The higher value interfacial modulus and elastic modulus of intersection is, the higher value interfacial strength and strength of intersection element shows. It is seen that the strength of interface element shows the value from 21MPa to 103MPa and that the strength of intersection element shows the value from 17MPa to 47MPa .

Figure 8 Three-dimensional graph of materials constants (strength of interface element).

Figure 9 Three-dimensional graph of materials constants (strength of intersection element).

CONCLUSION

In this study, combinations of material constants were determined using experimental results and numerical analysis. A method of specified material constants was proposed.

NOMENCLATURE

- a: Ratio of experimental value to calculated value of interface element
- a_c: Ratio of experimental value to calculated value of intersection element
- E_i: Elastic modulus of interface element
- E_c: Elastic modulus of intersection element
- T_i: Stress given in the model to be broken interface element
- T_c: Stress given in the model to be broken intersection element
- T: The initial microfracture stress obtained by experiment
- σ_i: Assumed strength of interface element
- σ_c: Assumed strength of intersection element
- σ_i*: Confirmed strength of interface element
- σ_c*: Confirmed strength of intersection element

REFERENCE

- [1]H.Hamada, N.Ikuta, Z.Maekawa, H.Ichihashi, N.Nishida, "Evaluation of the Interfacial Properties in the Embedded-single-fiber Coupon Test" *Composite Science and Technology*, 48 (1993) pp81-85.
- [2]L.T. DRZAL and M.MADHUKAR, "Fiber-matrix adhesion its relationship to composite mechanical properties", *Journal of material Science*, **28** (1993) pp569-610
- [3]H.Ichihashi, H.Hamada, N.Ikuta, and Z.Maekawa, "Effect of Silane Coupling Treatment on Microfracture in Plastic Reinforced with Plain Woven Glass Fabric", *SEN-I GAKKAISHI*, **Vol.49**, No.4, (1993) pp169-pp175.
- [4]A.Fujita, Z.Maekawa, H.Hamada and A.Yokoyama, *J. Rein. Plast. Compos.*, **11**, 600(1992)